

After a golden age and a lost decade, where next for academic digital publishing?

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Assessing the present condition of academic digital publishing may not be trivial, and it's even harder to predict its future trajectory, but we're on firmer ground when it comes to origins. Perhaps by looking back at where we've come from insights can be gleaned about where things might be heading. The roots of digital publishing in general go surprisingly deep and they spread widely. In part they lie in print production, but the picture there is not entirely straightforward. The development of DTP packages such as Aldus PageMaker (1985) and Quark XPress (1987), alongside the rise of personal computing, doubtless stimulated efforts to make prepress operations more efficient. Why should a typesetter have to key in an author's text when it's already been entered into a computer once by the author? Shouldn't editing be done in the digital domain rather than on paper, to reduce the risk of the typesetter mis-transcribing editorial markup? Perhaps editorial operations could be combined with styling and page layout, and PostScript output could then be delivered directly to the printer. Such seductive visions notwithstanding, it was early on realised, not least by STM publishers, that actually there were advantages in separating document style from structure. Pay attention to content role and semantics, get the structure right first, and style can be applied later with next to no effort, and simultaneously a basis is established for automating other content processing operations. (A failure to honour this 'structure first' principle persists in many style-led workflows, typically involving the heirs of the early DTP packages, where it hampers the creation of clean digital content.)

A key development was the release of SGML as a standard in 1986. Elsevier, if memory serves, began capturing all article abstracts in SGML marked-up form around 1990, in its 'CAPCAS' (Computer-Aided Production for Current Awareness Services) initiative. How did academic digital publishing evolve from that point on? Building on a talk I gave in September 2019 at a symposium on 'sustainable digital editions' organized by the Cambridge [University] Digital Humanities team, what follows is a personal, and at times slightly mischievous, take on a digital publishing timeline spanning the last three decades.

The 1990s

The early 1990s witnessed academic excitement about the overlapping notions of *hypertext* (customary genuflections at this point towards Vannevar Bush and Ted Nelson) and *textual*

non-linearity, the latter term resonating engagingly if superficially with the language of the sciences of complexity which were then in vogue. At the same time a certain physicist was – as any fule kno – busy joining the dots to create the Web. HTML, the most impoverished application of SGML the world had ever seen, soon became by far its biggest application as judged by scale of adoption. (The Text Encoding Initiative remained true to the spirit of SGML, however, if one can put it like that.) Once PDF had tamed PostScript for the screen, in 1993, it seemed possible to foresee the demise of print. Indeed, around the same time an article (or was it an entire special issue?) appeared in Byte magazine (R.I.P.) focusing on the [until very recently wholly risible] notion of the paperless office.

At roughly the same time, PCs were becoming powerful enough to support multimedia, as exemplified by the creation of the National Gallery's micro-gallery and the rise of companies such as Dorling Kindersley Multimedia. Awareness grew that digital information could embrace not just text and 2D graphics (bitmap and vector) but also audio and video, and beyond that 3D models, simulations, live equations, executable code... 1994 saw the Visible Human Project and VRML, the Virtual Reality Modeling Language. Interactive 3D models, hitherto the preserve of engineers, architects, chemists, and practitioners in other technical specialisms, suddenly looked like the next big thing. Fast forward a quarter of a century and we appear to be poised once more on the threshold of making routine a capability for the inclusion in digital publications of content types beyond text and static images. (Let's not rush, hey?)

Indeed, the mid-1990s had something of the character of a Golden Age. Some brilliantly sophisticated applications were developed around scholarly and research content; one thinks of the Oxford English Dictionary on CD-ROM, with proprietary indexing/retrieval technology developed by AND Software b.v. (handy aside: no, from a search/retrieval point of view it isn't a good idea to use a Boolean operator as a company name), or the OpenText-powered products developed by Chadwyck-Healey (now ProQuest). This was a time of waterfall development and rapid application development (RAD) techniques, bespoke software applications, SGML for text markup, powerful indexing and search functionality, and CD-ROM delivery. One person could realistically hope to master virtually all the technologies relevant to the development and delivery of an advanced digital content product. Ah, happy days!

In the later 1990s came the first wave of Web-based academic publisher platforms, e.g. Elsevier's ScienceDirect in 1997. ArXiv jumped the gun on the preprint server idea somewhat. (1991! Whatever were they thinking?) A major component of the later-90s technological zeitgeist was disenchantment with Windows – widespread concerns about Microsoft's dominance (which found a nice cultural expression in Douglas Coupland's novel *Microserfs*), the desire for an open standards-based Web, DLL conflicts, a sense that Unix was a more robust OS, etc. In response the open source movement was born, and with it the LAMP paradigm (Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl) that would dominate early Web development initiatives.

Markup evolves

Experience of working with SGML's complexities, meanwhile, and the success of HTML's simplicity, engendered in many a craving for a simpler markup standard. XML was the result, in 1998 (v1.0 specification); but disappointingly even as it made life simpler in some respects (no end tag minimization, etc.) it overlooked opportunities to simplify in others (e.g. around the handling of text encoding). It wasn't long before the markup world abandoned any commitment towards simplicity, with XML-related standards spewing out of W3C working groups like, well, let's just leave the simile hanging. Suffice it to say that XSLT ensured that writing document transformations would become a niche sport for techno-masochists, and killed off one conception of how XML documents might function. The limitations of DTDs gave rise to XML Schema. W3C Schemas had their own problems – but hey, at least they were written in XML! (What's that you say? 'So what?' Well quite.) So DTDs stuck around, but became unreadable agglomerations of parameter entities. This was something of a pity, given that readability had been one of the chief original virtues of DTDs. Compensatingly, however, HTML actually improved, the HTML5 + CSS3 combination making application-specific XML standards like JATS and BITS look (whisper it) ever so slightly clunky, while potentially obviating a complex transformation stage between raw content and rendered representation. There was an obvious tension, too, in relation to the JATS and BITS academic markup standards, between the aim to standardize and the desire for customizability. (It will be interesting to see whether JATS4R succeeds in squaring that particular circle.) It seemed telling that the biggest journal players stuck with their own proprietary XML formats.

A lost decade

Migrating academic content to the Web and plugging it into effective workflows took serious quantities of publisher time and resources, and the result was what from a user's perspective looks like something of a Lost Decade, which lasted until the later noughties. “Novel functionality? Forget it, let's just get the content up”; “all the user wants is a print replica”; “content is king”... Simultaneously the Google search interface paradigm – ‘don't bother the users' pretty little heads with anything more than a single text entry box’ – took hold and the information retrieval ergonomics, and perhaps sometimes even the substantive retrieval performance, of many applications of the time were no better, indeed were possibly significantly weaker, than they would have been ten years previously.

Hence it was possible to leave STM journals publishing in 1999 and return in 2012 to find that in terms of functional capability things had moved on surprisingly little. (One thing which had changed, however, was that Steven Harnad's railings against ever-growing Elsevier's scale and pricing power had now given way to an entire movement, pushing for something called Open Access, of which more anon...) In the first decade of the new millenium, meanwhile, software development had gone agile, or even Agile, and with that came a whole new raft of technologies, not least to support continuous integration and rapid

deployment. Presumably this was to compensate for the fact that few were able to reconcile Agile methods with an ability to meet firm deadlines for the delivery of defined packages of functionality. (Only joking!) During the Lost Decade along came Big Data, and, on the back of massively increased network bandwidth, computing 'in the Cloud' (i.e., Somewhere Else). And, of course, still more technologies – Hadoop, NoSQL databases, triple stores, etc. Languages continued to evolve. Data scientists were charmed by Python. Oracle took over Java and appeared to succeed in winding that particular party down, but up sprang Scala and Kotlin; and JavaScript spread like a fungus.

So to the present

In the later noughties Ebooks had seemed destined to supplant print, but the unmemorable reading experience (literally so, say psychologists) and myriad functional limitations meant that by 2015 or so it was clear they would be confined for the time being to a largely trade niche as a print counterpart. In 2017 the IDPF merged with the W3C (presumably still exhausted after its earlier orgy of XML-related standards creation), and the Ebook space looked – who's going to say it? – rather *boring*.

Around 2015 or thereabouts a second wave of publisher platform development came to fruition, employing responsive design techniques to service multi-device usage expectations, and making more use of hybrid data models – SQL, JSON, XML, graph databases. Third-party API-based integrations (earlier post-millennial efforts at web services based on WSDL and SOAP having come to nothing) supported new functionality, especially around metrics, annotation, and other paraphernalia associated with the burgeoning open research agenda. Artificial Intelligence techniques (well, sort of) entered the mainstream and finally – finally! – analysis of content semantics managed to crawl out of the lab and make its way meaningfully into digital products and services.

So we reach the present day. Open research is everywhere, mopping up a sizable fraction of scholarly publishing's figurative CPU cycles but also stimulating further innovation of platforms and business models. Above all, how to make it viable and equitable? One way to reshape the publishing cost base would be to have authors do more, and so we see the emergence of easy-to-use online authoring tools capable of outputting content in standard formats. (Which in a way takes us almost back to where this piece began.)

The costs of change

If any of the above is vaguely true, what can we say about overall trends? First, obviously, technological evolution isn't going to end, soon or ever. There will be ceaseless churn, with consequent needs for re-tooling, re-implementing, re-learning and re-training – and not without implications for digital preservation. Second, it seems as though never before has the business of creating and disseminating digital content been so hard, or costly. It takes armies of specialists to do almost anything, and that has implications for the sorts of people digital publishing needs. Rarely has the distance between technologists on the one hand, and content users, authors and curators on the other, been so great. That is emphatically not to

point a finger; it's just what happens when systems get complex and specialization intensifies. So now there's a need as never before for roles in publishing that major on translation, coordination, and management – and there's a premium on adaptability, helicopter thinking, on people with feet in both camps (tech-space and user-space), and on dynamic multi-functional teams. What can also now be clearly seen is how each wave of technology depends on, *and must support*, an associated cohort of specialist developers, implementers and adopters. Technology has to earn its keep.

In the space of digital information products and services germane to academic research it is tempting to suggest that we're still in the Precambrian phase. In other words it seems reasonable to predict proliferation of product and service types, differentiated and individuated by the diverse attributes of ramifying layers of technology, and sensitive to the ongoing evolution of research culture and values. But perhaps we need increasingly to distinguish between the books and journals realms. In relation to the former, we could do well to expect further diversification and hybridization of product models, content structures, data formats, languages, delivery mechanisms, roles, even assumptions about who should do what. In the face of such complex social, cultural and technological dynamics, it would not be surprising if at some point we see compensating efforts to contain the diversity through new moves towards standardization. Perhaps this will be imposed by the adoption of common infrastructure, whether arising from sheer innovation fatigue or more idealistic motives. Perhaps innovation will be most vibrant where user numbers are lowest, for with lower usage come simpler platform requirements and lower costs of failure. Will such innovation scale, though – and if it won't, does it matter? Possibly not, provided that discoverability and long-term preservation are ensured. That dual stipulation may prove to be no small thing, however.

Journals: a parallel (replacement) academic publishing infrastructure?

In the journals realm especially, patterns of change will be determined largely by the forces exerted by the burgeoning open research agenda. These will, I suspect, ultimately bring about more dramatic shifts in the tectonic plates of academic publishing than many currently dare to envisage. The realignments that occur will be both enabled by and will stimulate technological change, in the same way that the birth of the Web can be seen to be situated at a complex diachronic nexus of technological developments. And the Web may a very useful model for what is now required if the potential of open research is to be fully realised. That is to say, a transformative set of inter-related technologies, tools, standards and applications that enables a large community of users to achieve their over-riding goals with hitherto unobtainable ease. Currently we seem to be stuck in a quagmire, however, with piecemeal initiatives appearing left, right and centre that attempt to improve on one part of the academic publishing system whilst interacting successfully with all the other existing parts. The resultant welter of narrowly defined projects and services does little to improve the overall ability of researchers to accomplish their primary goals, or drastically simplify their working lives, and so the transition to open is occurring at only a modest rate. The frustration this engenders amongst the open activists leads them to resort almost exclusively to political tools, the aim being to coerce the

adoption of various ugly ducklings which, with luck and sufficient prayer, might over time develop into some kind of beautifully open research communications swan – but equally well might not.

To adopt another metaphor, the approach to reaching openness pursued to date, and exemplified by Plan S, could be compared to an attempt to replace a plane's fuselage whilst the plane is in mid-air. But rather than attempting massive 'in-flight re-engineering' of the existing scholarly communications system, which risks creating as many new problems as it solves, it would seem sensible to do what one does in any information systems project involving wholesale change: build a pilot of the new system which can be run alongside the existing system. Once the new system is proven, the old system can be retired. It would not be premature, after several decades of mudslinging, politicking and piecemeal tinkering, for interested stakeholders now to attend as a practical matter to the development of a parallel academic publishing infrastructure. I'm thinking here of a unified, global, end-to-end system that enabled authors to submit, with a single click, research outputs into a single academic content space, which would be indexed and clustered to enable readers to find content effortlessly according to multiple criteria.

To realise this vision would require academic institutions, societies and funders, as well as governmental bodies, to work together in concerted ways not yet witnessed, and moreover do so with an appetite for hands-on work that has been equally lacking to date. The starting point would need to be a fleshed out vision of the total user experience. But perhaps, as in the instructive case of the Web and Netscape Navigator, someone (or more likely, some team) is already quietly working to develop just such a system, and if so, perhaps its virtues will become so readily apparent as to initiate the dreamt of phase change in the academic communications space. (Something like SciELO may represent a template for large parts of such a system.) The technical ingredients for the system already exist, that seems certain. If anything is lacking, perhaps it is a potentially consensus-commanding vision of who does what, and of how funders, institutions, and ultimately societies, can be sure of the calibre of their researchers' work, once publishers are removed from the equation. If the idea of a replacement-née-parallel academic publishing infrastructure is the first provocation, here's the counter-provocation and coda: if it's taken several decades to get to a point where we still see no parallel infrastructure, perhaps that's an indication that it makes less sense to legislate publishers out of the equation than it does to leave them in.